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Dual Hybrid Training Meeting for Italian Judges

Padova, 22 December 2021

Analytical Résumé

1. Background

As part of the initiative “The Role of National Judges in the Enforcement of the EU-State Aid Law” (Action NatJEUSAL) funded by the European Commission - Directorate General for Competition, on 22th December 2021 took place at the University of Padova the third and last session of the training school for national judges in the field of European State Aid Law.

This event, alike the previous conferences at the University of Murcia (Spain) and Würzburg (Germany), pursued the aim of networking legal experts and judges from several Member States and confronting them with the recent developments of substantive and procedural State Aid Law and thereof enforcement at national level.

The meeting was intended as an opportunity to present the new Commission Notice on the enforcement of State Aid rules by national courts (2021/C 305/01) and to address open issues for the Italian jurisdiction. In particular, the execution at the national level of recovery orders relating to aid schemes and the profile of the protection of the legitimate expectations of the beneficiary, also in relation to possible cases of compensation of damages in connection with the liability of national administrative authorities, emerged as profiles of particular interest. From a substantive

point of view, the criterion of the State aid effect on trade between Member States in the context of administrative and judicial enforcement was also of particular interest.

The conference at the University of Padua, held under direction of Prof. Bernardo Cortese (Professor of European Union Law, University of Padova) started at 3.00 p.m. and included three main reports. Dr. Leonardo Armati (European Commission, DG Comp) presented the above-mentioned Commission Notice on private enforcement and its main novelties, Prof. Bernarndo Cortese analysed the requirement of State aid impact on Member States trade and Dr. Scuffi (President of the regional tax court for the Region Veneto) explained the contribution of the Italian courts on the subject. At the end, a debate took place among participants with the opportunity to submit observations, ask questions or even develop further themes in the field of European State Aid Law.

2. Implementation

2.1 Objectives achieved

The event was held both in a hybrid format and was attended by the speakers and by many representatives of the judiciary, including a representative of the *Scuola Superiore della Magistratura* and one of the *Consiglio di Presidenza della Giustizia Tributaria*, public administration staff, and university professors. This made it possible, as illustrated below, to deepen certain issues concerning the enforcement of European law on State aid at national level, as well as to convey to the judges notions and tools useful for understanding the structure of State aid control, so that they can be used not only in the judicial sphere, but also during the training of judges themselves. The number of participants amounted to thirty, mostly from Italy.

2.4 Description of activity

As first speaker introduced Dr. Armati the Commission Notice on private enforcement of July 2021. He started from the consideration that the results of the study commissioned by the Commission and published in 2017 on the status quo of private enforcement do not appear comforting. On the one hand, most of the cases analysed ended with a dismissal or did not leave room for a damage's

compensation. On the other hand, was noted a lack of knowledge by the judiciary on the interpretation of the concept of aid according to Art. 107 TFEU in complex cases. He also added that due to the direct effect of Art. 108 par. 3 TFEU acknowledged by the judgements of the CJEU judges can sanction violation of standstill obligation since legislative instruments of Member States are in any case more appropriate to provide protection to the claimants.

Judges must first examine whether the national measure is a State aid under the concept of Art. 107 TFEU, then if it is a new or existing aid. In this latter case, there is no violation unless the scheme has been modified amounting to new aid, in the former situation the judge must furthermore check whether the aid, is exempt from the notification and from the standstill obligation because of the application of a *de minimis* or an exemption regulation. Armati underlined also that the CJEU have ruled that conditions of application of those regulations must be interpreted restrictively, as this exemption does not constitute a transfer of competences towards the Member States. A violation of the e.g. General Block Exemption Regulation (GBER) by the Member State constitutes an infringement of Art. 108 par. 3 TFEU: this implies, on the one hand, that assurances from national authorities on the legality of the aid do not create legitimate expectations and, on the other, that the aid is not considered authorised. Therefore, the judge has to draw all inferences, according to national law, as regards the validity of measures giving effect to the aid, the recovery of financial support granted in disregard of that provision and possible interim measures.

Armati stressed the relevant role of the national courts in this case, since 96% of State aid is granted under the above-mentioned exemptions. In case of overlapping proceeding before a court and the Commission, often leading to conflicts of competence, both are required to assess the existence of an aid by interpreting the concept in accordance to Art. 107 TFEU; the Commission decision must nevertheless prevail in accordance to its exclusive competence on evaluating the compatibility of a measure, since its assessment could be otherwise jeopardised by a conflicting decision of a national court. A similar result would also occur in the case of a definitive judgement denying the existence of aid: the Commission's contrary decision would in any case prevail, as stated in the Notice on private enforcement. Its monopoly in examining the compatibility of aid would be otherwise

undermined, thus infringing against the European State aid law and preventing the recovery of the aid.

On the principle of *res judicata*, Prof. Cortese stressed that the recent case law of the CJEU (*Lucchini*, C-119/05; *Klausner Holz Niedersachsen*, C-505/14; *Buonotourist v Commission*, C-586/18 P) would be interpreted in a suggestive way by the Commission, suggesting a statement that the Court would have not yet fully made, as the national judgement did not concern the existence of an aid, even if it can be accepted that a question raised on this point would have an outcome like the one suggested. For Armati, however, this is necessary to prevent a potential conflict with the Commission, whose decision must prevail. This contrast can also generate from a further constellation, in which the Commission take a preliminary decision on a State aid and therewith opens a formal investigation on that measure. Although the outcome of the assessment is preliminary, the national court must draw all inferences from the presumption of the existence of the aid. It has to adopt appropriate measures, in order to safeguard the individuals affected by the measure, also through temporary injunctions, and cannot suspend the proceedings waiting for the final decision, otherwise it would allow the distortion of competition to continue.

In order to avoid potential conflicts between the judiciary and the Commission, the national courts can, on the one hand, apply the principle of sincere cooperation (Art. 4 par. 3 TEU), that of equivalence and effectiveness, just as that of procedural autonomy. They can, on the other hand, furthermore rely on means of cooperation, which have been improved by the Commission Notice on private enforcement in accordance to the regulation 2015/1589, as Armati pointed out. The national judges can ask the Commission to transmit information about State aid procedures before it or opinions on the general application of Art. 107, 108 TFEU, alike of regulation, guidance and notices on the field of State Aid. The Commission can also intervene as *amicus curiae* by submitting written observations when the case is particularly relevant or concerns new issues. Judges are also advised to send copies of issued judgments, that will be published on the Commission website.

Dr. Scuffi presented his considerations from the perspective of the Italian legal system and pointed out that the bulk of the litigation concerns the stage of the public enforcement, in particular the opposition to the recovery order issued by the State according to the negative decision of the Commission on the compatibility of the aid. The relevance of State aid in our legal system mainly concerns preferential tax treatment such as concessions, subsidies, reduction of tax base, exemptions, tax credits, deletion schemes. The means of granting the aid involves also the issue of the competent court jurisdiction. Unlike other Member States, in Italy the competence until 2012 lay by the tax courts (so called *commissioni tributarie*), which have a general jurisdiction in tax matters.

Law 234/2012 amended the Administrative Process Code and introduced Art. 133 co. 1 lit. z, which attributes to the administrative courts the competence on disputes concerning acts and measures granting State aid as well as recovery decisions. Such an exclusive jurisdiction has to be meant as a jurisdiction of acts and not of whole subject-matters or areas, which would be not consistent with the Italian Constitution pursuant to its art. 103. If the matter is assessed incidentally by the judge or raised by plea of the party e.g., in a fiscal matter, the tax court will be again competent. As well, the compensation of damages in favour of the third party against the beneficiary (under the profile of unfair competition in accordance to the provisions of the Italian Civil Code) fall within the jurisdiction of the civil court. The provision of the jurisdiction of the administrative courts addresses, however, a potential fragmentation of the judicial competences that would undermine the need for celerity and effectiveness in the recovery of the aid.

As matter of facts, the legislator had also foreseen an accelerated procedural lane: in the administrative field, on the one side, it can be resorted to an abbreviated judgement pursuant art. 119 Administrative Process Code, in the civil and tax field, on the other side, the rule on interim injunction plays an important role in State aid matters. The suspension of the act should anyway be limited only when there are plain doubts on the validity of the Commission decision: in that case, a preliminary ruling by the CJEU on validity is necessary. If the commission's decision is suspended on a temporary basis, the trial must be concluded before the tax court within sixty days, before the civil

one within ninety days, since the suspensive order will otherwise lose its effects. With the amendment to the Administrative Process Code and the new jurisdiction of the administrative courts, these tools have been nevertheless tempered, because the Italian courts had made imprudent use of the power of suspension of the Commission decision, thus disregarding that such an assessment, relying only on *periculum in mora* and *fumus bonis iuris*, undermined the effectiveness of the State aid control.

Prof. Roberto Schiavolin (Professor for tax law, University of Padova) tried also to provide a further explanation to the shift of competence in favour of the administrative courts. According to his analysis the tax courts protect taxpayers from an administrative action alleged to be unlawful, such as a denial of a tax relief, this circumstance making understandable the new administrative jurisdiction. In this latter case the third legitimated party or competitors complain about the illegal granting of aid to the beneficiary, while only apparently breaking up the aim reached at the beginning of 2000 within the Italian legal system with exclusive competence of the tax courts in tax matters. The goal is hence to provide an instrument to those who seek for safeguards against the unlawful granting of aid and to guarantee their legal standing before the national courts.

The last speaker, Prof. Cortese, shifted the focus of the conference to the substantive State aid law, by analysing the requirement of art. 107 TFEU on the aid impact on the trade between Member States. In the Commission notice of 2016 on the concept of State aid the effect on trade is examined very summarily, although in the context of State Aid Modernisation national administrative authorities should assess *ex ante*, also in accordance to this requirement, whether a future measure could be an aid. What nevertheless happens is a trivialisation of the criterion of the effect on trade, by considering it that the distortion of competition affects automatically trade. The *Tubemeuse* judgement (C-142/87) already emphasised the jurisdictional nature of this criterion as the definition of the scope of application of European Law or the permanent extension of the national provisions on the pending decision. In some decisions (e.g. *Komunala Izola Marina*, SA. 45220 2016; case law T-728/17) the Commission itself makes use of the possibility of qualifying a measure as capable or not of affecting trade, pointing out that there is no impact on trade where the limited nature of the

activity in question is considered and compared in the economic sector of reference, characterised through a high level of competition. Even the national court must interpret the concept of State aid pursuant to 107 TFEU in this way, despite the fact that the CJEU case law considers a mere potential effect on trade to be sufficient. The result cannot be however an automatic application, whereby if the effect cannot be ruled out, then it is always aid. This practice could hide a risk of turning State aid law into a general clause of strictly limited public intervention or equalisation between domestic competitors. Nevertheless, as some requests for preliminary ruling show, national authorities focus on not relevant case without any impact on trade, which consequently cannot be considered State aid pursuant art. 107 TFEU, thus disregarding also the aims of the State Aid Modernisation.

2.5 Feedback from participants

The event was an opportunity for representatives from the judiciary, public administrations and universities to share their knowledge and experience in the field of State aid. As emerged from the tenor of the questions, there was much appreciation on the part of the judges for the speakers' clarity in analysing the system of aid control and then transferring it, through examples based on concrete cases or established case law, to the Italian legal system. To be emphasised above all is the interest shown by the judges towards the cooperation tools offered by the new Communication as well as towards the need for a new awareness of Union law, to be strengthened also through increasingly frequent opportunities for discussion with the European institutions.

Not to be overlooked were also those interventions made during the debate that sought to explore new avenues that might allow State aid law not to overlook the needs and subjective legal situation of the beneficiary. In particular a proposal has been made to award damages not pursuant the lost enjoyment of the aid, but for an expectation generated by the conduct of an administrative authority. If, e.g., the authority misconstrues an aid or an aid scheme by applying in an improper way the GBER or another exemption tool, as emerged from some Italian court rulings, the damage produced, the recognition of which would not give rise to disguised aid, could be assessed on the loss caused by having made an investment based on the expectation of having the resources of the

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aid at its disposal. Finally, the effects of the Commission's preliminary decisions towards national courts and thus in terms of the protection of the beneficiary also aroused interest. Here we returned to the point by recalling the case law of the CJEU (*Eesti Pagar*, C-349/17; *Deutsche Lufthansa*, T-218/18), which has so far left no room for doubt, even in cases where a positive final decision of the Commission was later annulled, not recognising a legitimate expectation.

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The poster of the event was published on the website of the European Observatory on State Aid, a platform developed in cooperation with the Department of International and EU Public Law and the Veneto Region.

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The e-learning platform of the School of Law of the University of Padua (NatJeusal) has published the recordings of this and previous editions, study materials as well as the reports of the various meetings.

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Programme of the meeting

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Dipartimento di Diritto Pubblico
Internazionale e Comunitario

Nat J EU SAL

Incontro di studio

L'applicazione decentrata del diritto UE degli aiuti di Stato

22 dicembre 2021, ore 15-17 - Università di Padova, Sala Baldo e piattaforma Zoom

Relazioni:

La Comunicazione della Commissione relativa all'applicazione della normativa in materia di aiuti di Stato da parte dei giudici nazionali

Dott. Leonardo Armati, Commissione europea, DG COMP

Il contributo del giudice nazionale

Dott. Massimo Scuffi, Presidente, Commissione Tributaria Regionale per il Veneto,

La valutazione degli elementi della nozione di aiuto da parte dei giudici nazionali, con particolare riferimento all'effetto sugli scambi fra Stati membri

Prof. Bernardo Cortese, Ordinario di Diritto dell'Unione europea

A seguire

Dibattito con i partecipanti

- **il requisito degli effetti sugli scambi tra Stati membri**, in relazione alla nozione di aiuto di Stato, ai sensi dell'art. 107 TFUE, collocato nella diversa funzione di controllo svolta dal giudice interno sulle misure nazionali, rispetto a quella del giudice UE sulle decisioni della Commissione
- **la gestione**, a livello nazionale, **degli ordini di recupero relativi a regimi di aiuti e la relativa tutela giurisdizionale** (anche in correlazione con il profilo summenzionato)
- il profilo dell'**affidamento legittimo**, *oltre* la giurisprudenza relativa alla validità dell'ordine di recupero, ed in particolare **nell'ottica di un'eventuale responsabilità degli organi interni**

Con il sostegno di
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DG COMP – Direzione A

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